

Supplementary material for the paper:
How Practitioners Assess Software System Security

The Codebook

Table 1 presents our final codebook.

Table 1: The Codebook

Category	Codes
Human role	Actionable metrics/reaction, AI and ML role, changes, client or customer role, communication, context, context of vulnerabilities, critical/ high severity vulnerabilities external security review, false positives, final security responsibility, fix or not, fixing vulnerabilities/issues, human role, levels of security, metrics analysis, prioritization, resources, security awareness and knowledge, security review, security risk, security trainings, security-related role, severity of vulnerabilities/CVSS, verification, vulnerability analysis
Decision-making process	Prioritization, proof of metrics, usability and comprehensibility/metrics validation, rate at which new vulns are introduced, resources, security report, security review, security risk, severity of vulnerabilities/CVSS, shifting left, software reputation, stop support, testing, the impact of security issue, upgrade/update of software components verification, vulnerabilities in dependencies, vulnerabilities in software, vulnerability analysis
What is measured	Actionable metrics/reaction, assets/business value, attack surface, CI/CD pipeline, code review, comparison with the target value, compliance with standards/policies, critical/ high severity vulnerabilities, cumulative days open, dependencies development teams, exceptions, external security review, false positives, findings from tools/tools' report, fixing vulnerabilities/issues, incident, known vulnerabilities, license violation, maturity of adoption of practices, maturity of leadership, metrics trend/progress monitoring, misconfiguration monitoring traffic, need for metrics in the early phases, no metrics are involved, no need for the metrics in the early phases, no sense to measure, number of attack attempts, number of failed login attempts, prioritization, process security, programming languages, proof of metrics usability, comprehensibility/metrics validation, rate at which new vulns are introduced, rate at which vulns are fixed, repeated vulnerabilities, resources, SAST, secret scanning, security awareness and knowledge, security coverage/scope, security culture, security measures/controls, security risk, software development approach, testing, threat intelligence, threat modeling, threats, time to remediate/fix/recover, tools, unknown vulnerabilities/issues, upgrade/update of software components, vulnerabilities in dependencies, vulnerabilities in software, vulnerability age, vulnerability backlog, vulnerability discovery time, vulnerability found in forums weaknesses, docker images

Category	Codes
Security practices	AI and ML role, architecture and design review, build-breaker/threshold, code review, compliance with standards/policies, encryption, external security review, feedback, regarding security, metrics analysis, monitoring traffic proof of metrics usability and comprehensibility/metrics validation SAST, security awareness and knowledge, security measures/controls, security requirements, security review, security risk, security trainings, software development approach, testing, threat intelligence, threat modeling, upgrade/update of software components, vulnerability analysis
Metrics in the early phases	Architecture and design of software, architecture and design review, compliance with standards/policies, dependencies, need for metrics in the early phases, no metrics in early phases, no need for the metrics in the early phases, security by design, security measures/controls, security risk, severity of, vulnerabilities/CVSS, threat modeling, threats, time to remediate/fix/recover, vulnerabilities in software
Qualitative indicators	Architecture and design of software, dashboard, development teams, do not use the dashboards, management/board, metrics trend/progress monitoring, prioritization, qualitative indicators/visual representations, qualitative works better than quantitative, security awareness and knowledge, security risk, severity of vulnerabilities/CVSS, upgrade/update of software components, vulnerabilities in software
What is security	Architecture and design of software, assets/business value, compliance with standards/policies context, context of vulnerabilities, critical/ high severity, vulnerabilities, development teams, false positives, feedback, regarding security, infrastructure, levels of security, process, security, process security vs. outcome, qualitative indicators/visual representations, quality of software, rate at which new vulns are introduced, risk acceptance, security awareness and knowledge, security culture, security is about vulnerabilities, security is not about vulnerabilities, security posture is not one number, security product/outcome, security trainings, severity inaccuracy, software development approach, testing, threat modeling, time to remediate/fix/recover, tooling limitation. unknown vulnerabilities/issues, upgrade/update of software components, vulnerabilities in dependencies, vulnerabilities in software, what is security
What would like to measure	Architecture and design of software, effectiveness of security effort, reasons for not measuring, security awareness and knowledge, security community, security coverage/scope, security posture is one number, security posture/status, security trainings, the impact of security issue, threat modeling, threats, time to remediate/fix/recover, unknown vulnerabilities/issues, upgrade/update of software components, usage patterns, vulnerabilities in software
Reasons for not measuring	Architecture and design review, assets/business value, communication, context, human role, illegal, no way to measure, prioritization, resources, security awareness and knowledge, security culture, third-party responsibility, tooling limitation
Next steps in metric program	Automatic process, communication, critical infrastructure, critical reflection, dashboard, DAST, exploit of vulnerability, gather more metrics, human role, metrics availability, next steps, no next steps, prioritization, security coverage/scope, security observability, security trainings, security-related role, testing, threat modeling, tools, vulnerability analysis
Proof of metrics' reliability	Automatic process, CI/CD pipeline, collaboration internally, communication, comparison with the target value, compliance with standards/policies, context, context of vulnerabilities, dashboard, exploit of vulnerability, findings from tools/tools' report, human role, incident, majority of people, metrics analysis, metrics trend/progress monitoring, no metrics check, proof of metrics usability, comprehensibility/metrics validation, qualitative indicators/visual representations, qualitative works better than quantitative, security coverage/scope, security product/outcome, security-related role, triangulation, vulnerability analysis

Category	Codes
Demographic info	Company size, core business, current position, educational level, security responsibility of the interviewee, type of organization, type of software
How secure are you today?	Compliance with standards/policies, dependencies, incident publication, internal software security, concerns, levels of security, security posture is changing, security posture uncertainty, security posture/status, security product/outcome
Satisfaction with the measurements	Dissatisfied with the metrics, insecure about the metrics, qualitative works better than quantitative, quantitative works better than qualitative, satisfied with the metrics, satisfied with the qualitative indicators, somewhat satisfied with the metrics
What is ignored	DORA, false positives, findings from tools/tools', report, ignore all the metrics, logs, no ignorance, process security, qualitative indicators/visual representations, severity inaccuracy, software development approach, time to remediate/fix/recover, vulnerabilities in dependencies, vulnerabilities in software
Mental model: use of tools	Context, context of vulnerabilities, dashboard, DAST, false positives, findings from tools/tools' report, human role, SAST, severity inaccuracy, severity of vulnerabilities/CVSS, tools
Mental model: what to measure	Assets/business value, compliance with standards/policies, context, levels of security, one number for specific aspect, quantitative way, role of attacker, security measures/controls, security posture is changing, security posture is not one number, security posture is one number, security posture uncertainty, security posture/status, security risk, severity of vulnerabilities/CVSS, time to remediate/fix/recover, TTP, vulnerabilities in software
Mental model: symptoms of good process	Compliance with standards/policies, follow security practices, improvement in security, no design phase, no shifting left, security awareness and knowledge, security by design, shifting left
Mental model: search for vulnerabilities	Build-breaker/threshold, critical/ high severity vulnerabilities, false positives, fixing vulnerabilities/issues, levels of security, non-critical vulnerabilities (lows/medium), resources, security is not about vulnerabilities